

Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Hair Dye

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 26 Aug 2025

Keywords:

Herbal hair, dye
formulation, organoleptic,
Natural herbal

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.16951727

ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a 100% herbal hair dye using natural plant-based ingredients as an alternative to synthetic chemical dyes. Herbal dyes offer advantages such as safety, non-toxicity, scalp nourishment, and environmentally friendly properties compared to conventional dyes, which often cause irritation and hair damage. In this formulation, key herbal constituents including *Lawsonia inermis* (Henna), *Indigofera tinctoria* (Indigo), Aloe vera, Amla, Hibiscus, Beetroot, Coffee, and Black Catechu were selected for their dyeing and hair-conditioning properties. Various formulations (F1–F4) were prepared by adjusting the ratios of henna and indigo to achieve shades ranging from soft black to light brown. The prepared dyes were subjected to phytochemical, organoleptic, microscopic, and stability evaluations. Results indicated the presence of beneficial phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, and terpenoids that contribute to dyeing efficacy and scalp health. The formulations demonstrated good stability, effective coloration, and no adverse effects on hair or scalp. The study concludes that the developed herbal hair dye is safe, effective, eco-friendly, and suitable for all age groups, with potential to serve as a natural substitute for synthetic hair colouring products

INTRODUCTION

Natural Hair Dye Benefits.

Natural hair is a hair colouring product that is made from natural ingredients, such as herbs, fruits, and vegetables, instead of synthetic chemicals. this type of hair dye has gained popularity in recent years as people become more

conscious about the potential health risk associated with synthetic hair dyes.

One of the benefits of using natural hair dye is that it is gentler on the hair and scalp synthetic hair dyes often contain harsh chemicals like ammonia and peroxide, which can cause irritation and damage to the hair and scalp. Natural hair dye, on the other hand, typically uses ingredients like

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

henna, indigo, amla and beet juice, which are gentler and less likely to cause adverse reactions.

Another advantage of natural hair dye is that it can provide a more subtle and natural-looking colour. Synthetic hair dyes can often look overly bright or artificial, especially if the colour is not well-matched to the individual's skin tone or natural hair colour.

Natural hair dyes tend to create more nuanced shades that blend better with the individual's natural hair colour.

Mostly preferred the natural hair dye as compared to chemical hair dye because chemical hair dye causes skin-related diseases that's why natural herbal dyes are being preferred nowadays.

Herbal drugs without any adverse effect are used for healthy hair. The dyeing of hair is an ancient art that involves treatment of the hair with various chemical compounds. The need of herbal-based natural medicine is increasing. Fastly due to natural goodness and lack of side effect. Almost 70% of the population face the problem of balding and greying of hair.

The most widely used ayurvedic herbal drugs are amla, henna, traditionally used as hair colorant and for hair growth. Indigo, known as an initial fabric dye, indigo mixed with henna to make different light brown to black shades of hair dye.

A dye can generally be described as a coloured substance that has an affinity to the hair. The dye is generally applied as an aqueous solution, and may require a mordant to improve the fastness of the dye on the hair. Natural dyes are also referred to as mordant dyes. Different mordants will give different hues with the same dye. The mordant which allows the reaction between the dye and hair.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 plant source:

The following plant materials were collected from the garden and authenticated by the botanist. The materials were dried in shade and powdered.

1) Henna

The botanical name of Henna is *Lawsonia inermis*, which is the only species of the genus *Lawsonia* and belongs to the family *Lythraceae*. The leaves of this plant possess a red dye molecule called lawsone (2-Hydroxy-1-naphthoquinone), which has the ability to bond with the protein. The other components like Lawsone, 1, 4-naphthoquinone: 2-methoxy-3-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone, flavonoids, coumarins, phenolic acids: 5-10% gallic acid and tannins. Henna balances the pH of the scalp, preventing premature hair fall and greying of hair⁽²⁾

2) Black Catechu

The botanical name of Black Catechu is *Acacia catechu* / *Acacia chundra*. It belongs to the family *Leguminosae*. It is used as a colouring and dyeing agent.

3) Aloe Vera

The botanical name of Aloe Vera is *Gawar Patha*, it belongs to the *Liliaceae* family. Aloe Vera is effective for the scalp and can be used not only to treat hair loss, but to promote hair growth as well. Aloe Vera contains aloe emodin, which promotes hair growth by stimulating hair follicles. It is also useful in treating the scalp from sunburn. It is used as a natural mordant. It is also known for its emollient effect.

4) Indigo

The botanical name of Indigo is *Indigofera tinctoria* and Family Name *Fabaceae*. The indigo

Leaves are used to make hair dye as well as prepare medicated hair oil. leaf powder is used as a natural black colour dye for hair. Indigofera makes your hair more manageable, moisturized, protected with radiant shine The root is crushed and prepared into the decoction, and given for abdominal disorders, leucorrhoea, all types of toxicities etc. The leaves are crushed, prepared into a decoction, and given for toxicities, fever, arthritis etc. the leaf juice is given in the dose of 10-20ml along with honey twice daily for jaundice, inflammation of liver etc.

Table1: Formulation Composition

Sr no	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
1	Henna	2.5gm	4gm	6gm	7.5gm
2	Indigo	7.5gm	6gm	4gm	2.5gm
3	Aloe vera	2gm	2gm	2gm	2gm
4	Amla	2gm	2gm	2gm	2gm
5	Beet root	2gm	2gm	2gm	2gm
6	Hibiscus	2gm	2gm	2gm	2gm
7	Coffee	2gm	2gm	2gm	2gm
8	Black catechu	2gm	2gm	2gm	2gm

Fig 1: Formulation Of Herbal Hair Dye

Fig 2: combination of Henna and Indigo

- We have Chosen the combination of a Henna And indigo so that it produces the desirable color
- It is 100% Herbal dye
- As the other herbal dye includes the preservative and some chemical agent but we not use all these chemicals It gives desirable output after applying on hair without any side effect

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Practical Yield of Herbal Extracts

Name of extracts	Practical Yield
Henna	4.522gm (45.22%)
Black Catechu	2.878 gm (5.75%)
Aloe vera	35.152 gm (70.30%)
Indigo	16 gm. (80%)
Amla	1.347gm (2.5%)
Beet root	3.425gm (5.65%)

Hibiscus	25.34gm (60.43%)
Coffee	13.65gm (47.32%)

Phytochemical Study of Plant Extract

Table 3: Morphological Studies:

Extract	Colour	Odour	Taste
Henna	Reddish Brown	Characteristic	Bitter and Astringent
Black Catechu	Light brown to black	Odorless	Astringent
Aloe vera	Greenish brown	Characteristic	Bitter
Indigo	deep blue-purple	pungent	does not have a taste
Amla	light greenish-yellow	strong musky odor	sour and slightly bitter
Beet root	dark pinkish-red	distinct earthy odor	sweetness
Hibiscus	red	modest fragrance	sweet and sour
Coffee	soft greys	lightly caramelized and almost nutty	balance of bitterness, acidity, and sweetness

Phytochemical Screening

Table-4: Phytochemical Screening

Sr no	Phyto-constitutes	Henna	Indigo	Aloe vera	Amla	Beet Root	Hibiscus	Black catechu	coffee
1	Alkaloid	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+
2	Glycosides	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+
3	Flavonoid	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
4	Saponin	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	+
5	Carbohydrate	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
6	Terpenoid	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	+
7	Coumarins	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
8	Tannins	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
9	Anthraquinones	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+

Microscopic evaluation

Before applying hair dye on white hair dye on white hair

After applying hair dye and observe in 1 hour and observe in 1 hour

After applying hair dye and observe in 2 hour under microscope

Effect of hair dye on feather with lemon juice

1ST Day

2nd Day

3rd Day

Effect of hair dye on feather

Apply hair dye on feather

Day 1st

Day 2nd

- The lemon juice (Citric Acid) acts as a natural bleaching or oxidizing agent and when exposed to sun, it speeds up the bleaching process.
- The hair lightening effect is more evident in blonde and light brown hair.
- When you expose your hair to sunlight after applying lemon juice, the citric acid opens your hair cuticles. This strips away the first layer of hair color, resulting in a natural change in color

Stability Test-**Table 5: Stability Test**

Sr no	Parameter	Room Temperature	35° C
1	Colour	No change	No change
2	Odour	No change	No change
3	Texture	fine	Fine
4	Smoothness	Smooth	smooth

CONCLUSION

- It Can be wind up from the consideration that by convert the proportion of Henna and Indigo suitable light black, dark brown, medium brown, light Brown to obtain a hair.
- A PH is 6.67 is best for the penetration of hair colorant.
- We also added the aloe vera, amala, beet root, coffee to show the hair dye activity.
- We are also added the lemon juice as a different batch to see the effect, but we observe the herbal dye intensity increases with the lemon juice.
- The herbal base hair dye has been prepared.
- A hair dye colours the hair pack in combination almost gentle manner.

The most important advantage of herbal predicated cosmetic is nontoxic nature, no cause any irritation. it helps to treat dandruff by moving excess oil from scalp. Contamination, severe climate stress poorly affects the quality of their herbs. In this research we found effective properties of the herbal hair dye and further studied are needed to the performed to explore more useful benefits of this herbal hair pack .it is prepared form 100% water soluble ingredient. Basic material used in final product is totally environmentally -safe. Product stable at room temperature. The 100% pure herbal hair dye is

suitable for all age group. the mode of preparation and composition is environmentally safe

REFERENCES

1. Kumar KS, Begum A, Shashidhar B, Meenu M, Mahender C, Vamsi KS. Formulation and evaluation of 100% herbal hair dye. *International Journal of Advanced Research In Medical & Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2016;2.
2. Santhosham N, Jahnvi J, Mounika N, Vishnu N, Bhargavi R, Manjoorilhali SK, Vamsikrishna S, Aliya SD. Preparation and evaluation of herbal hair dye.
3. Jamagondi LN, Katte AS, Rumane MB, Mirza NN, Sontakke SS, Kale AR, Pathan MA. Development and evaluation of herbal hair dye formulation. *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2019;8(2):1363-5.
4. Rashmi Mallya & Padmini Ravikumar, Formulation and Evaluation of Natural Hair Colorants, *Int0. J Pharm. and Pharm. Sci.* ISSN- 0975-1491, 2015, 7, 3.
5. Madhusudhan Rao Y, Shayeda, Sujatha P. Formulation and evaluation of commonly used natural hair colourants, *Nat. Prod. Radiance*. 2008; 7(1):45-48.
6. Rajesh Yadav, Nita Yadav, Murli Dhar Kharya, Development and Evaluation of Polyherbal Formulation for Hair Colorant, *Res. J Pharma. Biol. and Chem. Sci.* 2014; 5(1):901. ISSN: 0975-8585. Jan-feb RJPBCS.
7. Bires Sarkar, Manish Devgan, Y. Ankamma Chowdary and Maddi Ramaiah, Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Gel Containing Extract of Cedrus deodara, *Int J Pharma Chem Sci*, ISSN: 2277-5005. 2015; 4(1): 67-70
8. Ahmad A, Mangaiyarkarasi R, Shahid W, Umar M, Shahina N, Rahmanullah S et al. Research Article Effect of Black Tea Extract

(Polyphenols) on Performance of Broilers.
Int. J Adv. Res. 2013; 1(7):563-566. ISSN NO
2320-5407.

9. Rangari.D.Vinod, Natural colorants and dye
In: *Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*,
(1stEd, Vol 1). Career publication, India,
2004, pp98-117.

HOW TO CITE: Ashvini Nagare, Chaitali Dongaonkar,
Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Hair Dye, *Int. J.*
of Pharm. Sci., 2025, Vol 3, Issue 8, 2840-2846.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16951727>

